

Application form Open Science Meetings

Do not adjust or delete any parts of this form. If you have any questions contact us.

1 Overview

1.1 Applicant details

1.1.1 Main applicant details

Title of the proposal*:	The Turing Way Book Dash – Dutch Hub
Applicant name: Title(s), initial(s), (prefix,) surname(s)	Dr E. Plomp-Peterson
E-mail:	e.plomp@tudelft.nl
Telephone number:	
Affiliation:	Delft University of Technology
Faculty/Department:	Faculty of Applied Sciences
Type of position:	Data Steward, permanent position

* This title should be the same as the title you enter in ISAAC.

1.1.2 Co-applicant details

You cannot add more than one co-applicant.

Applicant name: Title(s), initial(s), (prefix,) surname(s)	Dr. Carlos Martinez-Ortiz
E-mail:	c.martinez@esciencecenter.nl
Telephone number:	
Affiliation:	Netherlands eScience Center
Faculty/Department:	N/A
Type of position:	Scientific Community Manager, permanent position

2 Project description

2.1 Meeting details

Name of the meeting:	The Turing Way Book Dash – Dutch Hub
Location (city/venue):	TU Delft
Date (first day):	4-11-2024
Date (last day):	8-11-2024
Type of meeting:	International Scientific Meeting
Website (optional)*:	https://the-turing-way.netlify.app/community-handbook/bookdash

** If no event website exists, leave empty. If a website is made available after submission of this form, please inform us on opensciencemeetings@nwo.nl*

2.2 Relevance to Open Science

Indicate how your proposal relates to Open Science in your field or more broadly (do not exceed the maximum of 100 words).

Relevance to Open Science:	Book Dashes are contributor events to the Turing Way Handbook – a book on reproducible, ethical and inclusive data science. Any contributions to the book will be openly available under a CC-BY 4.0 license. These events bring together geographically diverse open science practitioners with shared interests that want to contribute their knowledge to The Turing Way. The Book Dashes are also inclusive events, ensuring a broad range of participation and operating under the Turing Way code of conduct. The event, and the community, are in full alignment with the principles of Open Science, and are a demonstration of how research communities can promote transparency, inclusivity, and accessibility in research and education. The Turing Way, and any contributions to the handbook and community, facilitate a more open research culture, and accessibility of data science knowledge and procedures.
-----------------------------------	--

2.3 Meeting description

Please describe the context, goal and (inter)national importance for Open Science of the proposed meeting (do not exceed the maximum of 200 words per item).

2.3.1 Context

This event is part of the broader efforts by The Turing Way to promote reproducible, open, collaborative and inclusive data science. The Turing Way organises their Book Dashes two times per year (May/June and November). A Book Dash facilitates contributions to The Turing Way Handbook and invites new people to join the community (see <https://the-turing-way.netlify.app/community-handbook/bookdash> for more details about the event). As part of these Book Dash events, there is generally an in-person component organised. Normally this in-person component is centered around The Alan Turing Institute, where the majority of the funding for The Turing Way originates. To ensure that The Turing Way remains a global community and handbook it is crucial to organise local hubs as part of the Book Dash. We have previously organised such Dutch in-person hubs with support from the TU Delft Library (<https://openworking.wordpress.com/2023/05/31/the-turing-way-book-dash-at-tu-delft/>, 2024), the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (in 2022) and the eScienceCenter (2024). With funding for Open Science activities being cut at TU Delft, we would no longer be able to organise a Dutch Hub at TU Delft without external financial support.

word count: 182 (max. 200)

2.3.2 Goal

The goal of a Book Dash event is to collaboratively create openly licensed educational resources in a short time period. By bringing together diverse teams of writers, editors, illustrators, and other contributors, Book Dash events facilitate rapid production while emphasising inclusivity and collaboration. The goal of an in-person hub is to solidify and expand the Dutch Turing Way network, by providing a space for them to come together during the Book Dash event. This will increase the awareness of The Turing Way community and available materials, and grow the Dutch contributions towards The Turing Way. Ultimately, the overarching objective is to contribute to the advancement of knowledge sharing and open science principles. As most of these open science principles work quite similarly across borders and domains, it is ideal to contribute to an existing resource instead of reinventing this wheel in various research communities. Dutch communities can also learn from the way that The Turing Way community is organised, and reuse materials and recommended practices for their own communities.

word count: 166 (max. 200)

2.3.3 (Inter)national importance for Open Science

The Turing Way is an international community and handbook that contributes to the advancement of Open Science principles. By organising a Dutch Hub within the Book Dash event, we ensure that the Dutch perspective and contributions are included in this global resource on reproducible, inclusive and ethical data science. The Turing Way offers recommended practices on many aspects of research that are globally relevant (and translated in multiple languages). The Turing Way fosters inclusivity and strives to make the adoption of reproducible and open data science as 'too easy not to do'. The Turing Way's impact lies ultimately in its role for driving the cultural change that is necessary for more open, collaborative and transparent scientific research.

word count: 117 (max. 200)

3 Programme

Describe the (provisional) programme of the meeting. (You may replace the text field below with a table or image)

The Turing Way Book Dashes are five working day long events where the online component is centered. The Dutch Hub will be an additional component to the event, where participants from the Netherlands (and neighbouring countries) can come together in person to join the Book Dash. This in-person component will take place during two days of the full event: on the Tuesday-Wednesday. This ensures that in-person participants also have sufficient time to join the online component of the Book Dash, so that the two events are sufficiently aligned and connected.

The online programme consists of five online sessions of 2.5 hours each, spread between 9:00 and 21:30 from Monday-Thursday. On Friday there are two share out sessions of 1.5 hours each.

The in-person Dutch hub will consist of two days in person, as described in detail below. The first day will start at 10:00 to ensure that people have enough time to travel to Delft, and will end earlier around 15:30 on the Wednesday to ensure that there is sufficient time for traveling back.

Tuesday 5 November

- 10:00 - Introduction & Getting to know each other / checking how to work together
- 12:00 - Lunch provided by university catering
- 13:00 - Working session
- 14:30 - Break
- 17:30 - Wrap up and setting goals for the next day
- 18:00 - Dinner at Faculty Club (short distance from the event location to ensure accessibility and this location is familiar with various dietary requirements)

Wednesday 6 November

- 09:00 - Start
- 10:30 - Shared break
- 12:00 - Lunch provided by university catering
- 13:00 - 15:00 - Working session
- 15:00 - 15:30 Wrap up & short share out
- 15:30 - Drinks/social at event location

Max. 2 pages (attachments are not allowed)

4 Participants

The meeting must be open to all possible participants in the Netherlands.

4.1 Number of expected participants

Indicate the total number of expected participants.

Number of participants from Dutch universities/universities of applied sciences/institutes/organisations/partners:	16
Number of participants from international universities/universities of applied sciences/institutes/organisations/partners:	4

Total number of participants:	20
-------------------------------	----

4.2 Distribution of participants

Indicate how many participants are expected from which universities/universities of applied sciences/institutes/organisations/partners. In the case of international participants, include at least the countries. Meetings are expected to have a diverse audience, meetings where all participants exclusively represent the applicant's organization, will not be funded.

Anyone is welcome to participate in the Book Dashes after filling out a short application form (see here for an example: <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1iEMoLPb8N-e36Vomvoug4ODw5cFIF4G7niZ4MYdDeY/>) to understand what they want to achieve during the Book Dash. The previous in-person hub (<https://openworking.wordpress.com/2023/05/31/the-turing-way-book-dash-at-tu-delft/>) had participants mainly from TU Delft, Vrije Universiteit and the eScienceCenter, as well as a group of five participants from German research institutes. We expect a similar distribution for the event in June 2024, and aim to have a wider spread from Dutch organisations this time. We would be happy to collaborate with TDCC projects where they are aligned with the goals of the Turing Way.

4.3 Distribution of speakers

Indicate how many speakers are expected from which universities/universities of applied sciences/institutes/organisations/partners. In the case of international speakers, include at least the countries.

We will not invite any speakers as this is a contributor/hackathon type of event.

5 Budget

5.1 Project Expenses and Revenues

5.1.1 Expenses

Please fill in one of the columns in the table below.

(Please note that not all items are eligible for funding).

	Budget
Eligible expenses:	
Costs for digital platform*	€0
Costs renting location + facilities	€0
Accommodation costs (coffee/tea/ lunch/ dinner / reception / overnight stay)	€2000 €100 per participant, expected maximum 20 which will be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two lunches (€250 each) • Two coffee breaks (€150 each) • Potential drinks (pending on the dinner budget (€100-230) • One dinner (€1200 maximum, pending on participation)
Travel and accommodation costs guest speakers(s)	€0
Costs child care (on site)	€0
Costs for making the meeting accessible for participants with disabilities	€0
Total eligible expenses:	€2000
Non-eligible expenses:	
Other attendance costs participants	€0
Costs organisation/professional congress organiser	€0
Other costs	€0
Total non-eligible expenses:	€0
Total (eligible + non-eligible) expenditure	€2000

5.1.2 Revenues

You may add rows to the table below to present the revenues.

Alan Turing Institute	€375 (€75 to make the event more accessible for participants with disabilities and/or childcare. Expected maximum is 5 participants)
-----------------------	--

Registration fees participants*	€0
Other revenues	€0
Total revenues	€375

**If applicable: indicate the total expected amount in fees*

5.1.3 Budget

Please note the maximum remuneration is € 100 per eligible participant, with a maximum of € 15.000,- for meetings.

Contribution requested:	€ 2000
-------------------------	--------

Are the total revenues (5.1.2) and contribution from Open Science NL (5.1.3) equal to the total expenditure (5.1.1)? If no, explain below.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no

5.2 Additional funding from NWO / Open Science NL

Have you applied, or will you apply, for any additional funding from NWO / Open Science NL for this meeting?

yes/no (If yes, please provide details).

Is NWO / Open Science NL contributing in any other way to this meeting, e.g. by offering a location or funding through another programme, such as a personal grant, or an NWA or KIC programme?

yes/no (If yes, please provide details).

6 Additional questions

6.1 Promotion of the meeting

How will you promote the meeting?

This event will be promoted via the existing The Turing Way communication channels (newsletter, Slack channel, social media, linked in and broader network). The applicant will use her network to ensure the Dutch Open Science Landscape is aware of this event, by asking the Netherlands Reproducibility Network and Open Science Communities to spread the word of the event, advertising the event at the upcoming Dutch Open Science festival (22 October), and using various research support networks (such as the DTL Data Stewardship) to spread the word. Any additional promotion by Open Science NL would be highly appreciated.

6.2 How will you publicise the funding awarded by Open Science NL?

If Open Science NL awards funding, then Open Science NL expects an acknowledgement of the financial support, for example through the placement of the Open Science NL logo on the programme or through an announcement.

How will you publicise the funding awarded by Open Science NL?

The financial support received if the funding is awarded will be acknowledged to inform the participants via the introduction presentation during the event, the programme that will be distributed to the participants, and the information email that is sent to participants before the event. We expect to write an overview blog of the event (like the last event: <https://openworking.wordpress.com/2023/05/31/the-turing-way-book-dash-at-tu-delft/>) where we will also acknowledge the funding. In addition, the support will also be acknowledged in some of the social media communications (LinkedIn and Mastodon).

7 Statements by the main applicant

By submitting this form I declare that:

Please check the boxes to confirm.

- By submitting this application form, I declare that I am appointed at my host institute until after the meeting that is applied for has taken place.
- By submitting this application form, I declare that I and all individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the *Netherlands Code of Conduct for Scientific Practice 2014* (Association of Universities in the Netherlands)
- By submitting this application form, I declare that I have discussed the final version of this proposal with all individuals involved in the organization of this meeting. All such individuals are aware of and agree with the content of this application.
- By submitting this application form, I declare I have taken notice of the rules for this call for proposals.
- By submitting this application form, I declare that I have completed this application form truthfully.

Name: Dr. Esther Plomp-Peterson

Place: The Hague

Date: 22 March 2024

Before you submit the proposal in ISAAC you will be asked to confirm again that you have completed the form truthfully.

Please submit the application to Open Science NL (pdf format is required!) via the online application system ISAAC, which can be accessed via the Open Science NL and NWO website. The application must be submitted from the account of the main applicant. For any technical questions regarding submission, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk (isaac.helpdesk@nwo.nl).